

**Silenced Desires and Objectified Bodies: A
Nussbaumian Reading of Perumal Murugan's *One
Part Woman* and *A Lonely Harvest***

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***Abstract:** This paper examines the representation of women's objectification and the silencing of their desires in Perumal Murugan's *One Part Woman* (2013) and *A Lonely Harvest* (2018). Focusing on the character of Ponna, it explores how women in rural Tamil Nadu are reduced to reproductive vessels and denied autonomy within patriarchal frameworks. American philosopher Martha C. Nussbaum's theory of objectification, particularly the notions of instrumentality, fungibility, ownership, denial of autonomy, and denial of subjectivity, provides the theoretical framework for analysis. The study reveals how Ponna's identity is constructed around fertility, with her worth tied to her ability to bear a child. In *One Part Woman*, her barrenness becomes the justification for social exclusion, emotional abuse, and the pressure to participate in the Ardhanarishvara festival. In *A Lonely Harvest*, widowhood compounds her objectification, leaving her vulnerable to stigma, exploitation, and the denial of individuality. The novels collectively highlight how patriarchal structures enforce silence upon women's desires, reducing them to instruments for familial and cultural continuity. By applying Nussbaum's framework, this paper underscores the dehumanising*

consequences of objectification and how patriarchal ideology erodes female agency and subjectivity. The analysis demonstrates that Murugan's narratives not only critique entrenched patriarchal practices but also foreground the necessity of feminist re-readings of Indian literature.

Keywords: Perumal Murugan, Objectification, Female Desire, Patriarchy, Nussbaum, Indian Literature, Tamil Literature

Introduction

Perumal Murugan, one of the foremost voices in contemporary Tamil literature, has persistently engaged with the intersection of caste, patriarchy, and sexuality in rural Indian society. His novels often foreground marginalized voices and reveal the silences embedded in cultural traditions. *One Part Woman* (2013) and its sequel *A Lonely Harvest* (2018), translated by Aniruddhan Vasudevan, constitute two of Murugan's most poignant narratives. Both novels follow the life of Ponna, a woman trapped in the contradictions of love, fertility, and societal expectations. Her personal journey illustrates how patriarchal frameworks consistently objectify women and suppress their desires under the guise of cultural obligation and familial duty. The third novel in the series, *Trial by Silence* (2018), is written from the perspective of Kali as he withdraws from Ponna, and breaks all ties with her (Sengupta 98). However, since Ponna's perspective is the point of view for this research, the third novel is outside the scope of the present study.

Patriarchy in rural Tamil Nadu, like in much of India, locates women's worth within narrowly defined roles—primarily wifehood and motherhood. A woman unable to conceive is considered incomplete, sometimes even cursed, her barrenness treated as both a social and spiritual deficiency. Fertility becomes not only a personal aspiration but also a cultural demand that ties female identity to reproduction. Murugan situates Ponna's struggles within this context: despite her love for her husband Kali, her inability to bear a child subjects her to ridicule, pressure, and

threats of abandonment. This reveals how patriarchal structures reduce women to reproductive vessels, stripping them of individuality and autonomy.

The objectification of women in such contexts can be examined through Martha C. Nussbaum's theory of Objectification, articulated in her seminal text *Sex and Social Justice* (1999). Nussbaum identifies seven dimensions of objectification—instrumentality, denial of autonomy, inertness, fungibility, violability, ownership, and denial of subjectivity (*Sex*). These dimensions capture how women are “dehumanized” and treated as “things” rather than persons with agency (Nussbaum “Objectification” 249). In Murugan's novels, several of these dimensions resonate strongly. Ponna is treated as an instrument to produce an heir; her body is regarded as the property of her husband and family; her desires and subjectivity are disregarded in the pursuit of social acceptance. Nussbaum's framework thus provides a critical lens to expose the mechanisms through which women's identities are shaped and silenced (Malinauskaite 2).

While Murugan's *One Part Woman* has been widely discussed for its exploration of caste, culture, and sexuality, there is comparatively less critical engagement with *A Lonely Harvest*, which extends the narrative to Ponna's life after Kali's death. The sequel illuminates how widowhood exacerbates women's marginalization, subjecting them to new forms of social exclusion. Ponna, even after bearing a child through the temple ritual, is reduced to a figure of stigma and is denied dignity in her roles as mother and widow. By examining both novels together, this paper demonstrates how objectification persists across different phases of a woman's life, rendering her perpetually vulnerable to patriarchal control. While previous scholarship has examined Murugan through ecofeminism, cultural theory, and disability studies, few have foregrounded the systematic reduction of women to objects in his narratives. Moreover, *A Lonely Harvest* has received limited attention in feminist criticism, despite its rich portrayal of the afterlives of objectification. The present paper contributes to this

discourse by offering a comparative reading of the two novels, highlighting how patriarchal ideology not only suppresses female desires but also constructs women's identities, beginning as early as their childhood, as contingent upon male authority and social approval (1).

The significance of this inquiry extends beyond literary analysis. In Indian society, where debates on gender equality and women's autonomy remain pressing, literature provides a mirror to cultural practices and a critique of entrenched inequalities. Murugan's novels, set in colonial-era Tamil Nadu, expose how women continue to be denied autonomy and silenced in matters of sexuality, fertility, and self-expression. In sum, this study argues that *One Part Woman* and *A Lonely Harvest* together dramatize the continuum of female objectification—from barrenness to widowhood—illustrating how women's worth is persistently measured against patriarchal standards.

Theoretical Framework

The concept of objectification has been a central concern in feminist theory, particularly in exploring how women are reduced to “objects, things or commodities” that serve patriarchal needs (Nussbaum “Objectification” 249). Among the many contributions to this discourse, Martha C. Nussbaum's theory of Objectification, articulated in *Sex and Social Justice* (1999), offers one of the most comprehensive frameworks. Her model is especially significant for literary analysis, as it allows scholars to identify multiple dimensions of dehumanisation and apply them to characters and narratives that reflect lived realities of women.

Nussbaum outlines seven dimensions of objectification:

1. Instrumentality – treating a person as a tool for another's purposes.
2. Inertness – regarding the person as lacking in agency or activity.

3. Fungibility – seeing a person as interchangeable with others of the same type.
4. Violability – perceiving the person as lacking boundary integrity and subject to violation.
5. Ownership – treating the person as property that can be controlled or transferred.
6. Denial of autonomy – viewing the person as lacking in self-determination.
7. Denial of subjectivity – ignoring the feelings and experiences of the person.

These categories do not always occur in isolation; rather, they overlap in ways that reveal the depth of patriarchal domination. For instance, when a woman is pressured to bear children, her body becomes an instrument of lineage (instrumentality), she is denied the right to refuse (denial of autonomy), and her emotions are disregarded (denial of subjectivity). Together, these dimensions expose the mechanisms through which women are stripped of individuality and reduced to objects of male or societal use. Applied to literary texts, Nussbaum's framework allows critics to examine how narratives encode the reduction of women to passive roles. Objectification is not only sexual but also social and cultural: it frames women's lives as vessels of continuity rather than as autonomous existences. In patriarchal societies, women's bodies and identities are often constructed as commodities to be exchanged, controlled, or violated for the preservation of family honour, caste purity, or religious tradition (Parveen and Radhakrishnan 55). These insights are particularly relevant to Perumal Murugan's novels, which foreground women's struggles within rigid rural communities.

In *One Part Woman* (2013), Nussbaum's notions of instrumentality, fungibility, and ownership is especially evident. Ponna is treated as an instrument to produce a child; her inability to conceive renders her replaceable, much like cattle that can be exchanged. Her body is treated as belonging not to herself but to her husband and mother-in-law, who make decisions about her

participation in the temple festival without her consent. These narrative moments exemplify how patriarchal structures enact objectification by controlling women's "reproductive capacities" (Reissman 112). In *A Lonely Harvest* (2018), the sequel, the dynamics shift but the objectification persists. Widowhood, instead of liberating Ponna, further entrenches her vulnerability. Here, Nussbaum's categories of denial of autonomy, denial of subjectivity, and violability become central. Ponna's choices are disregarded as her community dictates where she should live and how she should behave. Her grief, desires, and aspirations are silenced, while her role is confined to the preservation of caste honour and maternal duty. The text also portrays how widows are socially "violable"—susceptible to exploitation and exclusion because of their status (Nussbaum "Objectification" 258).

Importantly, the framework highlights that objectification is not merely about physical or sexual reduction but also about systemic social and cultural silencing of women (Jose 3360). Women's emotions, aspirations, and subjectivity are often denied validity, which reinforces their marginalisation. Murugan's narratives dramatise this silencing by showing how Ponna's voice is consistently overshadowed by societal expectations.

Thus, the theoretical framework provides two critical benefits for this paper:

1. It allows a close textual reading of Ponna's experiences as structured by objectification.
2. It situates Murugan's narratives within broader feminist debates on autonomy, identity, and the politics of desire.

The analysis that follows demonstrates how *One Part Woman* and *A Lonely Harvest* serve as cultural critiques of patriarchal oppression, exposing the systematic denial of women's humanity in colonial rural Tamil Nadu.

Analysis of *One Part Woman*

At the heart of *One Part Woman* lies the question of fertility. Ponna and Kali's childlessness after twelve years of marriage becomes not only a personal grief but a social scandal. Some abominable socio-cultural customs like child marriage and celibacy in widowhood had entered the 19th century rural Tamil Nadu society (Karthika and Suganya 29). Motherhood was treated as the central marker of a woman's worth, while barrenness believed to render her incomplete. In light of this, Ponna's body is viewed primarily as a medium to fulfill the reproductive function; her identity is subordinated to the community's demand for an heir (Jose 3362). This aligns with Nussbaum's notion of instrumentality, where a person is treated as a tool for another's purposes ("Objectification" 257). The village elders suggest to Kali that Ponna is just like "some cows" who "never get pregnant" and advise him to "change the cow" (Murugan *One* 10). Such stark imagery also reveals how barren women are equated with unproductive livestock—replaceable, disposable, and stripped of individuality. This echoes Nussbaum's category of fungibility, as Ponna's value is tied not to her unique identity but to her ability to serve a reproductive function ("Objectification" 260). The emotional turmoil of being treated as an interchangeable thing further underscores the depth of objectification.

The central event of the novel, the Ardhanarishvara chariot festival, epitomises how women's autonomy is erased in the pursuit of patriarchal continuity. For a night, marital rules are suspended, and women are encouraged to sleep with strangers to conceive children. Ponna's mother-in-law insists that she participate, framing it as a divine opportunity to overcome her barrenness. Yet, strikingly, Ponna's consent is never sought. Decisions are made by her husband and family, treating her body as property to be managed. Here, Nussbaum's notion of denial of autonomy becomes crucial as Ponna's agency is undermined; she is treated with "ownership" as she is coerced into embodying the community's reproductive expectations (262). Even when she

expresses willingness, it is framed in conditional terms— “I will, if you are fine with it” (Murugan *One* 117)—demonstrating that her choices are contingent upon male approval rather than personal choice. Her subjectivity is subsumed under patriarchal control, illustrating how systemic silencing operates within cultural traditions.

Though Kali loves Ponna deeply, his behaviour also reflects ingrained patriarchal attitudes. Their intimacy often prioritises his desires, reducing her to an object of male satisfaction (Parveen and Radhakrishnan 49). He visits her when he wishes, yet neglects her emotional needs. Ponna, in turn, suppresses her own desires, embodying Nussbaum’s denial of subjectivity—her emotions and aspirations are ignored, while her body becomes the site of others’ will and purpose (“Objectification” 265). This denial is compounded by social stigma. Ponna is barred from rituals, excluded from communal life, and mocked by neighbours. Her pain is invisible to society, which focuses only on her inability to bear a child. The silencing of her voice—both within her marriage and community—exemplifies the structural erasure of female subjectivity.

The festival also raises the issue of caste. Kali fears that if Ponna conceives with a lower-caste man, both she and the child would be deemed impure. This again reflects the category of ownership, where a woman’s body becomes the repository of caste honour, belonging to her husband and lineage rather than to herself. Nussbaum is critical of Kant’s ignorance towards the “asymmetrical or hierarchical nature of marriage,” and believes that marriages often fail due to this arrangement (“Objectification” 269). In *One Part Woman* Ponna’s worth is measured not by her identity but by the purity of her womb, reinforcing how patriarchy and caste intersect to objectify women. Kali on the other hand is a man caught between his desire for a child and his love for his wife. His painful yet derogatory shout towards the end, “You whore! You cheated me! ‘You will not be happy’” (Murugan *One* 240) is the vilest expression of the delusion he lived in.

In *One Part Woman*, Murugan exposes the manifold ways in which patriarchal culture objectifies women: reducing them to instruments of reproduction, denying their autonomy, disregarding their subjectivity, and treating their bodies as repositories of caste purity. Through Ponna's struggles, the novel illustrates how systemic pressures dehumanise women, eroding individuality and silencing desires. Nussbaum's framework provides a powerful lens to uncover these layers of oppression, showing how objectification functions not only at the interpersonal level but also through cultural traditions and social hierarchies.

Analysis of *A Lonely Harvest*

A Lonely Harvest begins after Kali's tragic death, positioning Ponna in a vulnerable space as both widow and mother. In traditional Tamil society, widowhood stripped women of dignity, marking them as inauspicious. Ponna, despite conceiving through the temple festival, is ostracised and denied participation in rituals. This reflects Nussbaum's dimension of violability—her existence is treated as lacking boundary integrity, open to exploitation, exclusion, and social violation ("Objectification" 257). Her worth, once tied to fertility, is now overshadowed by the stigma of widowhood (Karthika and Suganya 31). As a widow, Ponna embodies contradiction: revered symbolically as pure, yet treated socially as polluted. She becomes a paradoxical figure, simultaneously life-giver and social outcast. The denial of her humanity underscores the deep entrenchment of patriarchal norms.

Women in 19th century Tamil society were denied basic human rights, as elucidated by Karthika and Suganya; Ponna's desires—emotional, physical, and existential—remain suppressed in widowhood (31). While she longs for companionship and dignity, her community polices her every choice. She is expected to withdraw from public life, maintain silence, and submit to cultural prescriptions. This is a textbook instance of denial of autonomy and denial of subjectivity. Her grief for Kali is never acknowledged in full human terms; instead, her behaviour is

judged against societal expectations. By refusing her the right to express longing or desire, patriarchal society reduces her to an empty vessel, one whose sole function is maternal duty. Her individuality is effectively erased. Motherhood, which in *One Part Woman* was denied to Ponna, becomes a reality in *A Lonely Harvest*. Yet instead of liberating her, it further binds her identity to patriarchal definitions of womanhood (Sujatha 44). Ponna is recognised only as a mother, not as an autonomous being. Her individuality remains silenced, demonstrating how objectification adapts rather than disappears. Here, Nussbaum's instrumentality re-emerges ("Objectification" 257). Ponna's role is confined to nurturing her child, fulfilling the community's demand for lineage continuity. Her identity is reduced once more to functionality, reinforcing the idea that a woman's value is contingent upon serving family and society.

Just as in *One Part Woman*, in the sequel too caste continues to shape Ponna's objectification. Her child, conceived through the festival, raises questions of lineage and purity. Society regards both mother and child through the lens of caste hierarchy, illustrating Nussbaum's ownership; Ponna's body and its reproductive outcome are seen as belonging to family honour, not as personal experiences. The idea that her intimacy with a stranger taint her purity reduces her body to a symbol of collective identity, rather than her self-identity (Divya and K. 261). *A Lonely Harvest* extends Murugan's critique of patriarchy by showing how widowhood does not free women but deepens their objectification. Through stigma, silencing, and the reinscription of identity around motherhood, Ponna remains trapped in patriarchal expectations. The novel illustrates how objectification persists across life stages, and "plurality of features" of the "cluster-term" can be applied, such as in Ponna's case, shifting from barrenness to widowhood but never allowing her full subjectivity (Nussbaum "Objectification" 258). The various categories—particularly denial of autonomy, denial of subjectivity, violability, and ownership—illuminate the layered processes through which Ponna's individuality is systematically erased.

Discussion

Perumal Murugan's *One Part Woman* and *A Lonely Harvest* together present a continuum of female objectification, illustrating how patriarchal ideology constrains women's lives across different stages—marriage, barrenness, motherhood, and widowhood. When read through Martha Nussbaum's theory of objectification, these novels reveal how systemic forces deny women autonomy, silence their desires, and reduce them to instruments of cultural and familial continuity. The discussion that follows synthesises the findings from both analyses and situates them within larger feminist discourses.

In *One Part Woman*, Ponna is primarily objectified through the lens of fertility. Her inability to conceive renders her replaceable, subject to ridicule, and coerced into practices that deny her agency. Fertility becomes the sole measure of her worth, reducing her to an instrument for lineage. In *A Lonely Harvest*, objectification persists but takes new forms: widowhood transforms her into a stigmatized figure, vulnerable to social exclusion and denied recognition as a full human being (Sengupta 96). Together, the novels demonstrate that objectification is not confined to one stage of life but adapts to ensure women's subordination throughout their existence. This continuity echoes Simone de Beauvoir's observation in *The Second Sex* (1949) that women are "not born" but made—their lives are shaped in compliance to male authority (330). Murugan's narratives dramatize this by showing how Ponna's desires are consistently overshadowed by social obligations, first as a barren wife, then as a widow and mother.

A striking feature of both novels is the systematic silencing of female desires. In *One Part Woman*, Ponna's yearning for motherhood is framed not as her personal aspiration but as society's demand. Her own emotions are denied validity, as even her willingness to attend the chariot festival is contingent upon her husband's approval. In *A Lonely Harvest*, her longing for dignity, companionship, and selfhood is similarly suppressed, as her grief

and aspirations are deemed irrelevant to cultural prescriptions of widowhood. This reflects Nussbaum's categories of denial of subjectivity and denial of autonomy, where women's feelings and choices are disregarded. It also resonates with Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's argument in "Can the Subaltern Speak?" (1988) that women in patriarchal societies are "doubly in shadow"—first due to colonial or cultural authority, and second by the structures of patriarchy itself (84). Ponna embodies this double silencing, her voice mediated through the expectations of family, caste, and community.

Both novels also highlight the intersection of patriarchy and caste. Ponna's body becomes the repository of caste honour, particularly in *One Part Woman*, where Kali fears her intimacy with a lower-caste man during the festival. In *A Lonely Harvest*, questions of lineage continue to haunt her child, reinforcing how caste hierarchies inscribe themselves upon women's bodies. Nussbaum's notion of ownership is central here. Ponna's body does not belong to her but to her husband, family, and community. Her sexuality is regulated not only to ensure reproduction but also to preserve caste purity. This mirrors Uma Chakravarti's argument in *Gendering Caste* (2003), which asserts that women in caste societies are controlled as custodians of lineage and purity (30). Murugan's fiction illustrates how this control translates into objectification, where women's bodies are stripped of individuality and transformed into communal property.

Motherhood operates as both aspiration and burden in the novels. In *One Part Woman*, Ponna's yearning for motherhood drives her to endure humiliation and coercion. In *A Lonely Harvest*, motherhood finally materialises but does not liberate her; instead, it confines her identity even further, reducing her to maternal function. This paradox underscores how patriarchal culture constructs motherhood as the essence of womanhood while simultaneously denying mothers autonomy and respect. Adrienne Rich's *Of Woman Born* (1976) is instructive here, distinguishing between the "experience" of motherhood (potentially empowering)

and the “institution” of motherhood (patriarchal and controlling) (ix). Murugan’s novels capture precisely this tension: while Ponna’s desire for a child reflects her emotional yearning, the social institution of motherhood constrains her, objectifying her body and silencing her individuality.

Although Murugan’s novels are set in colonial-era Tamil Nadu, their concerns resonate strongly with contemporary society. Women across India—and globally—continue to face pressures linking their worth to fertility, family honour, and conformity to patriarchal roles. Practices such as child marriage, widow stigmatisation, and fertility-related discrimination persist, albeit in transformed ways. By dramatising these issues through Ponna’s story, Murugan critiques not only the past but also the enduring structures of gender inequality. Furthermore, applying Nussbaum’s theory highlights how objectification is not merely interpersonal but systemic. It is embedded in cultural rituals, familial expectations, and caste hierarchies. Recognising these layers is crucial for feminist critique, as it shifts the focus from individual acts of oppression to the cultural logic that sustains them. Murugan’s narratives, therefore, invite readers to confront the deep-rooted nature of patriarchy and the urgent need for change.

Conclusion

Perumal Murugan’s *One Part Woman* and *A Lonely Harvest* together present a powerful critique of the systemic forces that reduce women to objects within patriarchal society. Through the story of Ponna, Murugan dramatizes how women’s identities are constructed not by their own desires but by social expectations tied to fertility, motherhood, caste honour, and widowhood. When examined through Martha C. Nussbaum’s theory of objectification, the novels reveal how women are persistently subjected to instrumentality, fungibility, denial of autonomy, denial of subjectivity, violability, and ownership. These forms of objectification not only silence female voices but also erode the very foundations of individuality and agency.

In *One Part Woman*, Ponna's worth is equated with her capacity to bear a child, reducing her to an instrument of reproduction. She is treated as fungible, comparable to cattle, and her autonomy is consistently undermined by familial and social pressures. In *A Lonely Harvest*, widowhood and motherhood reinscribe objectification in new forms. Ponna, though a mother, remains socially stigmatized and denied recognition as a full human being. Across both narratives, the silencing of her desires underscores the systemic denial of subjectivity, illustrating how patriarchy controls not only women's bodies but also their emotional and existential realities. Such analysis underscores that liberation cannot be achieved merely by altering women's roles within patriarchy; rather, it requires dismantling the cultural logics that sustain objectification itself.

Ultimately, Murugan's novels compel readers to recognise the silent suffering of women like Ponna, whose desires are denied and whose humanity is eroded by patriarchal norms. Literature here functions as resistance, exposing the structures of oppression and imagining the possibility of feminist re-readings that restore women's subjectivity. Future research may build upon the study of objectification by exploring intersections of caste, religion, and sexuality in Murugan's works, thereby broadening the understanding of how systemic objectification operates in diverse cultural contexts.

Works Cited

- Ali, Nazir. "The Human and the Non-Human in Perumal Murugan's *One Part Woman*. *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, vol.4, no. 2, 2016, pp. 661-664.
- Beauvoir, Simone De. "Formative Years: Childhood" *The Second Sex: Lived Experience*, Vol. II, eBook, Vintage Books, 2011, pp. 330-394.
- Chakravarti, Uma. *Gendering Caste: Through A Feminist Lens*. Revised ed., Sage Publications, 2018.
- Ghosh, Utsarga. "Understanding Tamil Gods and Contextualising Religious Customs in Perumal Murugan's *One Part*

- Woman.” *Research Trends in Language, Literature and Linguistics*, vol. 3, no. 2, 2024, pp. 6-12.
- Jose, Brijji. “One Part Woman: The Book on Trial for Acknowledging the Invisible.” *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, vol. 8, no. 9, 2019, pp.3360-3363.
- K, Kowshigan. “Exploring Social Disability in Perumal Murugan’s *One Part Woman*.” *International Journal of English Language, Education and Literature Studies*, vol. 3, no. 3,2024. <https://ijeel.org/issue-alldetail/exploring-social-disability-in-perumal-murugans-one-part-woman>.
- Kant, Immanuel. *Lectures on Ethics*. Translated by Louis Infield, 1963.
- Lavanya, S. “The Blues and the Greens in Perumal Murugan’s *One Part Woman*.” *Local Color Literature*, edited by S. Prabahar, Shanlax Publications, February 2023, pp. 52-56. ISBN: 978-81-19042-19-7
- Lerner, Gerde. *The Creation of Patriarchy*, Oxford UP, 1986.
- Malinauskaite, Kristina. “Perpetuation of Sexual Objectification & Silencing of Women.” U of Colorado at Denver.
- Millet, Kate. *Sexual Politics*, Columbia UP, 1970.
- Murugan, Perumal. *One Part Woman*, translated by Aniruddhan Vasudevan, Penguin Books, 2013.
- Murugan, Perumal. *A Lonely Harvest*, translated by Aniruddhan Vasudevan, Penguin Books, 2018.
- Nussbaum, Martha C. “Objectification.” *Philosophy & Public Affairs*, vol. 24, no. 4, 1995, pp. 249–91. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2961930>. Accessed 28 Sept. 2025.
- . *Sex and Social Justice*, Oxford UP, 1999.
- Parveen, Azeena and Radhakrishnan, Vineeth. “Female Body as the Other: Ritual Biotechnical Approach using Perumal Murugan’s *One Part Woman* and *Matrubhoomi*: A Nation without Women.” *Studies in Media and Communication*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2023, pp. 48-57. <https://redfame.com/journal/index.php/smc/article/view/5941>.

- Rawat, P. S. "Patriarchal Beliefs, Women's Empowerment, and General Well-being." *Vikalpa*, vol. 39, no. 2, 2014, 43-56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090920140206>
- Rich, Adrienne. Introduction. *Of Woman Born: Motherhood as Experience and Institution*, W.W. Norton & Company, 1986, pp. ix-xxxv.
- Riesman, Catherine Cohler. "Stigma and Everyday Resistance Practices: Childless Women in South India." *Gender & Society*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2000, pp. 111-135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/089124300014001007>.
- Sujatha, S. "Feminine Quest for Freedom: A Re-reading of Ponna-Perumal Murugan's *One Part Woman*." *An international, Peer Viewer, referred, E-Journal in English*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2022, pp. 40-46. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=703878308004>.
- Saranya, R. and Jerome, J. Charly. "Psychological Impact of Culture on The Life of a Childless Couple in *One Part Woman*." *Impressions: An International Refereed e-Journal of English Studies*, vol. XIII&XIV, no. II&I, 2020, https://impressions.org.in/jul19/ar_rsaranya.html.
- Sengupta, Rituparna. "Book Review: *Trial by Silence* and *A Lonely Harvest* by Perumal Murugan, Anirudhan Vasudevan." *Journal of Language, Literature and Interdisciplinary Studies*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2019, pp. 26-101.
- Spivak, Gayatri C. "Can the Subaltern Speak?" *Colonial Discourse and Postcolonial Theory: A Reader*, edited by Patrick Williams and Laura Chrisman, Columbia UP, 1994, pp. 66-111.
- Tamilarasi, C. "Status of Women In Tamil Nadu through the Ages.", *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, vol. 2, no. 6, 2020, pp. 407-409.
- Trivedi, Ritumbara and Rekha Tiwari. "Patriarchal System and The Condition of Women." *A Peer Reviewed Journal of English Literature*, vol. 7, no. 4, 2016. <https://anubooks.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/N-4.-2016-21.pdf>.

- Walby, Sylvia. "Theorizing Patriarchy." *Sociology*, vol. 23, no. 2, 1989, pp. 213–34. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/42853921>.
- Wilfred W, Sheena. "Cultural and Woman in Perumal Murugan's *One Part Woman*." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, 2019, pp. 500-507. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1906I99.pdf>.
- Zecchini, Laetitia. "When My Own Writing is My Enemy: Notes on Perumal Murugan and an Interview." *South Asia Multidisciplinary Academic Journal*, vol. 31, 2023. <https://journals.openedition.org/samaj/90>.